

Ideal Research

An International Multidisciplinary e-Journal (ISSN- 2454-857X)

(Peer Reviewed Journal) Impact Factor: 2.835 (I2OR)

**Volume-10, Issue-3,
August -2024**

Website

www.idealresearch.in

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ISSN: 2454-857X
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Peer Reviewed Journal

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Scheduled Castes in India: Study of Historical Marginalization, Governmental Departments, and State-wise Population

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Abstract:

This paper explains the socio-economic status of Scheduled Castes (SC) in India, tracing their historical marginalization and contemporary governmental interventions. Rooted in ancient scriptures, the caste system entrenched social hierarchies, with SC communities facing discrimination for centuries. Colonial rule worsened their plight, but the 20th century witnessed the emergence of reform movements led by figures like Gandhi and Ambedkar. Post-independence, India enacted constitutional safeguards and established welfare departments at state and central levels to uplift SCs. Methodologically, data from the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment and state government websites were gathered to understand SC population distribution. Findings reveal significant regional disparities in SC percentages across states. While each state has dedicated departments for SC welfare, regions with higher SC populations require intensified efforts to promote equity and empowerment. In conclusion, despite constitutional protections and governmental initiatives, challenges persist in achieving equitable SC upliftment. Further research is needed to evaluate the effectiveness of welfare policies and address socio-economic disparities among SC communities, emphasizing the importance of collaboration between governments and grassroots organizations for meaningful change.

Keywords: Scheduled Castes, Social Welfare Department, Population Distribution, Regional Disparities, Governmental Efforts, Upliftment, Socio-economic Development, Resource Allocation, Policy Implementation.

Introduction:

The historical background of Scheduled Castes in India is deeply rooted in the complex socio-political fabric of the country, marked by centuries-old systems of social stratification and discrimination. The term "Scheduled Castes" refers to those communities historically subjected to social, economic, and political marginalization due to their caste status within the traditional caste hierarchy. This hierarchical system, known as the caste

system, categorized individuals into rigid social groups based on birth, occupation, and perceived purity. The origins of the caste system can be traced back to ancient Indian scriptures, which provided religious justification for the hierarchical division of society. According to these texts, society was divided into four main varnas or castes, namely Brahmins (priests and scholars), Kshatriyas (warriors and rulers), Vaishyas (traders and merchants), and Shudras (laborers and artisans). Below the varna system were the "Dalits" or "Untouchables," who were considered outside the caste system and subjected to severe social ostracism and discrimination. Throughout history, Dalits and other marginalized communities faced systemic oppression, including social segregation, denial of access to education and religious institutions, and exploitation in various forms. They were relegated to menial and degrading occupations, such as manual scavenging and leather work, and were often subjected to violence and abuse by higher-caste communities.

During the colonial period, British rulers in India reinforced caste-based discrimination through laws and policies, worsening the conditions of Dalits. However, the early 20th century saw social reform movements led by figures like Gandhi, Ambedkar, and Phule, advocating for Dalit rights and social equality. The term "Scheduled Castes" was formalized in the Government of India Act of 1935, and later incorporated into the Indian Constitution post-independence, acknowledging the need for special measures to uplift historically marginalized communities.

After India gained independence, existing states recognized the need to uplift the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes within their respective jurisdictions. As part of their efforts, many states established Departments of Social Welfare or similar bodies to address the socio-economic needs and provide welfare measures for these marginalized communities. Concurrently, the central government played a significant role in urging and supporting states to establish such departments, emphasizing the importance of addressing the socioeconomic needs of these communities. Through policies, guidelines, and funding support, the central government facilitated the establishment of welfare mechanisms at the state level, promoting the well-being and empowerment of Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes. The Constitution of India reflects deep concern for the upliftment of Scheduled Castes, Scheduled Tribes, and Other Backward Classes through various articles and provisions. It abolishes untouchability (Article 17), mandates special care for their educational and economic

interests (Article 46), and ensures reservation in appointments (Article 335). Articles 15(4) and 16(4A) provide for special provisions and reservations in promotions. Additionally, Articles 338, 330, and 332 establish bodies and provisions for their representation in governance. The Ministry of Social Justice & Empowerment oversees the interests of Scheduled Castes.

Evolution of the term “Scheduled Caste”

Scheduled caste is a term coined by Simon Commission in 1935, in its bid to schedule or list castes which were backward in all respects compared to the other castes in Indian society. The purpose was to identify depressed and oppressed groups in society and to give them certain benefits and privileges to uplift them. When India gained independence in 1947, and when the Constitution was adopted in 1950, the government of India used the same term to refer to the downtrodden in society. Various welfare schemes were developed as part of their constitutional protection. However, not much has been achieved with these schemes. “The scheduled castes continue to be the most disadvantaged group in the Indian population... Their backwardness is evident from the comparative figures on their preponderance in rural areas, low literacy rate, dependence on agriculture, and massive employment as agriculture laborers. The reason for this can be located in government administration, in the attitudes of Hindus, and even in the lack of adequate organization of the scheduled castes themselves.”^[1]

Research Methodology:

Data was obtained from the Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment - the Government of India's official website, along with detailed research on individual state government websites. It facilitated the comprehensive collection of information regarding the Scheduled Caste (SC) population across India's states and union territories. This data includes both the total SC population and the percentage of the SC population relative to the total population, this data is gathered and presented to offer a nuanced understanding of the demographic landscape. Visual representations in the form of bar charts were generated to illustrate the distribution of the SC population across different regions, enhancing accessibility and clarity. Furthermore, bar charts depicting the percentage of SC population about the total population were created. By integrating authoritative government data and

employing visual aids, this research aims to provide a scholarly exploration of the SC population distribution, offering insights into socio-demographic dynamics and disparities. Through rigorous analysis, the study contributes to the scholarly discourse on social justice, empowerment, and equitable development initiatives for marginalized communities in India.

Research Objectives:

1. Analyze the distribution of the Scheduled Caste (SC) population across Indian states and union territories.
2. Investigate regional disparities in SC prevalence and socio-economic status.
3. Assess the effectiveness of governmental efforts and welfare policies for SC upliftment.
4. Explore the implications of SC population concentration on resource allocation and policy implementation.

States with a population of Scheduled castes as per the 2011 Census of India^[2]

Sr. No.	State/UT	Total Population	SC Population	% of SC Population	Department related to Upliftment of Scheduled Castes
1	Uttar Pradesh	199812341	41357608	20.7	Department of Social Welfare, Uttar Pradesh
2	West Bengal	91276115	21463270	23.51	Backward Classes Welfare Department, West Bengal
3	Bihar	104099452	16567325	15.91	SC and ST Welfare Department, Bihar
4	Tamil Nadu	72147030	14438445	20.01	Adi Dravidar and Tribal Welfare Department
5	Andhra Pradesh	84580777	13878078	16.41	Social Welfare Department, Government of Andhra Pradesh
6	Maharashtra	112374333	13275898	11.81	Social Justice and

					Special Assistance Department, Government of Maharashtra.
7	Rajasthan	68548437	12221593	17.83	Social Justice and Empowerment Department, Government of Rajasthan.
8	Madhya Pradesh	72626809	11342320	15.62	SC and ST Welfare Department, Madhya Pradesh
9	Karnataka	61095297	10474992	17.15	Backward Classes Welfare Department, Government of Karnataka
10	Punjab	27743338	8860179	31.94	Department of Social Justice, Empowerment and Minorities, Government of Punjab
11	Odisha	41974218	7188463	17.13	ST & SC Development, Minorities & Backward Classes Welfare Department, Government of Odisha
12	Haryana	25351462	5113615	20.17	Social Justice & Empowerment, Welfare of Scheduled Caste & Backward Classes Department

					and Antyodaya Department, Government of Haryana
13	Gujarat	60439692	4074447	6.74	Social Justice and Empowerment Department, Government of Gujarat
14	Jharkhand	32988134	3985644	12.08	Department of Scheduled Tribe, Scheduled Caste, Minority and Backward Class Welfare, Government of Jharkhand
15	Chhattisgarh	25545198	3274269	12.82	Department of Tribal and Scheduled Caste, Government of Chhattisgarh
16	Kerala	33406061	3039573	9.1	Scheduled Caste Development Department, Government of Kerala
17	NCT of Delhi	16787941	2812309	16.75	Welfare of SC/ST, Government of NCT of Delhi
18	Assam	31205576	2231321	7.15	The Directorate of Welfare of Scheduled Castes, Assam
19	Uttarakhand	10086292	1892516	18.76	Social Welfare

					Department, Government of Uttarakhand
20	Himachal Pradesh	6864602	1729252	25.19	Empowerment of SCs, OBCs, Minorities & Specially Abled, Government of Himachal Pradesh
21	Jammu & Kashmir	12541302	924991	7.38	Social Welfare Department, Directorate of Social Welfare, Kashmir.
22	Tripura	3673917	654918	17.83	Department for Welfare of SCs, Government of Tripura
23	Chandigarh	1055450	199086	18.86	Department of Social Welfare, Women and Child Development, Chandigarh Administration.
24	Puducherry	1247953	196325	15.73	Adi Dravidar Welfare and Scheduled Tribes Welfare Department, Government of Puducherry, India.
25	Manipur	2570390	97042	3.78	Social Welfare Department, Government of Manipur
26	Sikkim	610577	28275	4.63	Social Welfare

					Department, Government of Sikkim.
27	Goa	1458545	25449	1.74	Goa Commission for Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes
28	Meghalaya	2966889	17355	0.58	Social Welfare Department, Government of Meghalaya.
29	D & N Haveli	343709	6186	1.8	Social Welfare Department, UT of Dadra and Nagar Haveli, Daman, and Diu.
30	Daman & Diu	243247	6124	2.52	Social Welfare Department, UT of Dadra and Nagar Haveli, Daman, and Diu.
31	Mizoram	1097206	1218	0.11	Social Welfare and Tribal Affairs Department, Government of Mizoram
32	Arunachal Pradesh	1383727	0	0	-
33	Nagaland	1978502	0	0	-
34	A & N Islands	380581	0	0	-
35	Lakshadweep	64473	0	0	-
	INDIA	1210569573	201378086	16.63	-

The following chart illustrates the population of Scheduled Castes across various states and union territories in India.

The following chart illustrates the percentage of the Scheduled Caste population relative to the total population of various states and union territories in India.

Data Interpretations:

In conclusion, the provided data highlights the following key points:

- **Total population:** States differ greatly in terms of the overall population; states like Sikkim, Goa, Arunachal Pradesh, and Mizoram have comparatively small populations, whereas states like Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, and Bihar have large populations. States with higher population densities might encounter more difficulties in developing their infrastructure, allocating resources, and providing services. These states' governments must put policies into place that adequately serve the requirements of their sizable and diversified people.
- **Regional Disparities:** There is significant variation in the percentage of Scheduled Caste population across different states and union territories in India. For instance, while Punjab has the highest percentage at 31.94%, Himachal Pradesh is in second place with 25.19%,

and West Bengal is in third place with 23.51%. states like Goa, Meghalaya, and Mizoram have much lower percentages, with some states even having negligible SC populations.

- **Governmental Efforts:** Each state and union territory has established specific departments dedicated to the upliftment and welfare of Scheduled Castes. These departments have varying names and functions but share the common goal of addressing the socio-economic needs of the SC population.
- **Population Concentration:** In regions where the population of Scheduled Castes (SCs) is notably high, the concerned departments must prioritize and intensify their efforts towards upliftment. This entails implementing targeted interventions focused on education, skill development, healthcare, and economic opportunities tailored to the needs of SC communities. Collaboration with grassroots organizations and community leaders is crucial for the effective implementation and monitoring of welfare schemes. By concentrating resources and attention in these regions, governments can work towards fostering greater social equity, inclusion, and empowerment for SCs.

Limitations of the Study:

The study relies on census data 2011 due to the absence of a 2021 census, due to the COVID-19 pandemic's impact in India. Owing to the diversity and complexity of the population, no forecasting techniques or trend analyses were employed to estimate population figures. Instead, the study prioritized the use of the most recent available data to ensure accuracy and reliability in its research approach.

Scope of Further Study:

Due to time and word limitations in the paper, an exhaustive examination of various departments about the social upliftment of scheduled castes is omitted. However, a comprehensive analysis of different schemes and their efficacy and a comparative evaluation of their strategies for the upliftment of scheduled castes can be conducted. Subsequently, recommendations and guidelines can be provided to states with suboptimal performance in social welfare initiatives.

References:

1. Mankidy, A. (1976). Scheduled Caste Entrants into the Banking Industry on JSTOR. *Economic and Political Weekly*. <https://doi.org/4364406>

2. *State/UT-wise SCs Population, 2011: Ministry of Social Justice and Empowerment - Government of India.* <https://web.archive.org/web/20210305124048/http://socialjustice.nic.in/UserView/index?mid=7663>
3. Akhtar, Z. (2020). Scheduled Castes, Dalits and Criminalisation by ‘descent.’ *State Crime Journal*, 9(1), 71–99. <https://doi.org/10.13169/statecrime.9.1.0071>
4. Mosse, D. (2018). Caste and development: Contemporary perspectives on a structure of discrimination and advantage. In *World Development* (Vol. 110, pp. 422–436). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2018.06.003>
5. Desai, S., & Dubey, A. (2012). Caste in 21st Century India: Competing Narratives. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 46(11), 40–49.

Webliography:

1. <http://samajkalyan.up.gov.in/en>
2. <https://www.anagrasarkalyan.gov.in/>
3. <https://state.bihar.gov.in/scstwelfare/CitizenHome.html>
4. <https://www.tn.gov.in/department/1>
5. <https://socialwelfare.apcfss.in/>
6. <https://sjsa.maharashtra.gov.in/en>
7. <https://sje.rajasthan.gov.in/Default.aspx>
8. <https://mp.gov.in/sc-st-welfare-department>
9. <https://bcwd.karnataka.gov.in/english>
10. <https://punjab.gov.in/government/departments/department-of-welfare-of-scs-bcs/>
11. <https://stsc.odisha.gov.in/>
12. <https://sewa.haryana.gov.in/>
13. <https://sje.gujarat.gov.in/?lang=English>
14. <https://www.jharkhand.gov.in/welfare>
15. <https://tribal.cg.gov.in/en>
16. <https://www.kerala.gov.in/departmentdetail/MjU3NDA5MzYuNzY%3D>
17. <https://scstwelfare.delhi.gov.in/>
18. <https://socialjustice.assam.gov.in/>
19. <https://socialwelfare.uk.gov.in/>

20. <https://socialwelfarekashmir.jk.gov.in/>
21. <https://scw.tripura.gov.in/>
22. <https://chdsw.gov.in/>
23. <https://adwelfare.py.gov.in/>
24. <https://socialwelfare.mn.gov.in/en/>
25. <https://sikkim.gov.in/departments/social-welfare-department>
26. <https://www.goa.gov.in/department/goa-commission-for-scheduled-castes-and-scheduled-tribes/>
27. <https://megsocialwelfare.gov.in/about.html>
28. <https://ddd.gov.in/social-welfare-department/>
29. <https://socialwelfare.mizoram.gov.in/page/welcome-to-directorate-of-social-welfare>
30. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Caste_system_in_India
31. <https://vikaspedia.in/social-welfare/scheduled-caste-welfare-1/scheduled-caste-welfare-in-india#:~:text=Scheduled%20castes%20are%20those%20castes,who%20need%20special%20consideration%20for>